

у викладання молекулярної біології: 87–94% респондентів відзначили краще розуміння молекулярних механізмів захворювань, 78–88% – розвиток навичок інтерпретаційних та консультативних навичок, понад 90% – зростання мотивації.

Ключові слова: медична освіта; кейс-метод; штучний інтелект; фахові компетентності; молекулярна біологія.

Mykhailova Alla, Yanitska Lesia. AI - Enhanced Case-based Learning for Professional Competency Development in Molecular Biology Teaching.

The article is devoted to the justification of the case method with elements of artificial intelligence as an effective pedagogical tool for the formation of research and analytical competencies of applicants for higher medical education in the process of studying the discipline «Molecular Biology». The purpose of the study is to generalize theoretical and practical approaches to combining the case method with artificial intelligence tools and to assess its effectiveness in the formation of molecular biological knowledge, research and clinical and consultative skills of medical students. The methodological basis of the study was the analysis of modern scientific sources, methodological modeling, pedagogical observation, student questionnaires and analysis of the results of educational activities. For practical verification of the approach, a clinical and molecular case «Hereditary breast cancer» was developed and tested, supplemented by the use of artificial intelligence for the generation of variable tasks, data interpretation and modeling of genetic counseling. The survey (n = 84) demonstrated the effectiveness of integrating the case method and AI in teaching molecular biology: 87–94% of respondents noted a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms of diseases, 78–88% noted the development of interpretative and advisory skills, and over 90% noted increased motivation.

Keywords: medical education; case-based learning; artificial intelligence; professional competencies; molecular biology.

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DESIGN THINKING IN CULTURAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

1 Introduction: The relevance of cultural entrepreneurship

The cultural and creative industries are considered an important economic sector, comprising 238,000 companies and two million employees [1, p. 6]. Economically, cultural enterprises can contribute to economic growth, generate start-ups and innovations, and create jobs on their own initiative. They have the potential to compensate for deficits in public cultural activities with new products or services and to raise awareness of the arts and culture market [13]. In recent years, there has been a shift from a cultural sector that is supported by the public sector to an economically oriented field of cultural and creative industries [9, p. 1]. In view of limited government resources, the idea of securing cultural value creation through entrepreneurial independence and market-oriented action is gaining in importance. This requires an understanding of culture that requires user-oriented creativity and innovation from those involved [18].

The focus on utility poses a challenge in the cultural sector. Cultural professionals are often accused of not always working in a utility- or market-oriented manner. This phenomenon stems from the artistic logic of action, which differs from entrepreneurial logic. Cultural workers are generally guided by aesthetic, content-related, or social goals; they work according to an «art-immanent logic» with the idea that artistic value is independent of audience success or market response [10]. Entrepreneurship, however, is primarily guided by the expectations and needs of customers. The focus is on creating value for others [14]. The two logics can lead to tensions, as projects or products that focus on individual forms of expression may not achieve economically viable demand. At the same time, excessive adaptation to audience preferences carries the risk of losing artistic integrity. The aim of cultural entrepreneurship is to find a balance between artistic authenticity and value creation. The goal is to create offerings that are culturally valuable and at the same time connect with the needs of the audience.

Design thinking offers a way to systematically combine artistic authenticity with the value creation desired in the context of entrepreneurship.

2 Understanding the concept of cultural entrepreneurship

Cultural entrepreneurship is still a young discipline; the term was first introduced in 1982 and has been gaining momentum since the 2000s. Currently, two fields of action can be identified in cultural entrepreneurship. One field focuses on entrepreneurial activities in the cultural and creative industries and the arts. Culture is understood as a sector in which entrepreneurial activity takes place, particularly in the form of start-ups. The second field of activity views culture as an integral part of all sectors and examines how entrepreneurs use cultural resources to legitimize their businesses or which socio-cultural factors shape entrepreneurial behavior in different cultures [4]. This article follows the narrower understanding of the term, which encompasses entrepreneurial thinking and action in the cultural sector.

The term refers to the specific activity of founding cultural enterprises or bringing cultural or creative products and services to market that embody cultural value but also have the potential to generate financial returns. In a broader sense, it also refers to the creation, facilitation, or dissemination of cultural offerings or the solution of cultural tasks in an entrepreneurial manner. Cultural entrepreneurship encompasses both self-employment or the establishment of a business and the development of cultural entrepreneurial innovations within dependent employment (cultural intrapreneurship) [7]. The arts and culture industry generally comprises eleven different submarkets and encompasses all artistic, literary, cultural, musical, architectural, or creative services, works, and products [21].

The arts and culture industry consists mainly of small and micro-enterprises, is strongly anchored in urban, creative milieus, and often produces individualized products (including one-offs) or prototypes in small batches. This goes hand in hand with a high degree of agility, but also with low economies of scale and economic vulnerability [5]. This is often the case in the cultural and creative industries, as production is characterized more by individuality and originality than by mass production [5]. In addition, the pressure to innovate in the industry is exceptionally high because many business models are based on the continuous and rapid creation of new products and services—for example, seasonal or release-related, as in the case of films, books, music albums, fashion collections, or marketing campaigns.

3 Innovation impulses and benefit orientation through design thinking

Since the 2000s, design thinking has increasingly been understood as a response to creative work under uncertainty in the economy. Design thinking is a benefit-centered, creative, and iterative method for solving complex problems. It combines analytical thinking with creativity and focuses on people's needs in order to develop innovative solutions [16]. The process typically involves five phases: understanding users through empathy, evaluating results and defining a point of view, gathering ideas, developing prototypes, and testing these prototypes with users (see Figure 1).

In **phase 1** (developing empathy), the affected stakeholder group and its needs are analyzed in detail in order to understand the problem of a potential target group. This is particularly relevant for cultural enterprises, as cultural offerings are often symbolic and subjectively evaluated experiential goods [3] and at

Figure 1: Process model of design thinking [15; 16].

the same time address a heterogeneous audience and other stakeholders (e.g., funding institutions, scenes, communities). Through observation, interviews, and analysis of the use of cultural offerings, an in-depth understanding of target groups is created, which is often lacking in the arts and culture sector or is too intuitive. In **phase 2** (defining a position), the insights gained are evaluated and condensed into a clear problem focus. The use of personas helps to reveal and balance different and sometimes contradictory expectations—for example, between artistic and economic logics [5]. Since cultural enterprises often operate in hybrid financing structures and are embedded in local creative clusters, defining the problem helps to precisely consider relevant perspectives (audience, funding logics, partner networks). In **phase 3** (idea generation), as many possible solutions as possible are generated. This is crucial for the cultural and creative industries, as this is where the content-related and aesthetic innovations on which soft innovation is based originate [22]. Structured idea generation systematically expands on intuitive ideas and promotes new formats, meanings, and forms of expression. At the same time, it enables early comparison with usage needs and exploitation requirements, so that soft innovations are not only creative but also compatible and feasible. In **phase 4** (prototyping), the most promising ideas are quickly transformed into simple and tangible models. Since cultural products can only be evaluated through experience and many creative professionals have limited resources [13], simple prototypes (e.g., made of paper) enable cost-effective and low-risk testing of cultural offerings before large resources are invested. In **phase 5** (testing), the prototypes are tested with the target group and further developed based on their feedback. Since the markets in which cultural enterprises operate are strongly influenced by reputation, community ties, and cultural connectivity, testing not only provides feedback but also opens up opportunities for co-creation, i.e., the joint development of ideas with the audience or relevant communities. Especially in an industry where value creation is often socially embedded and cultural products are created through resonance, co-creation increases the relevance, acceptance, and anchoring of new offerings [20]. This reduces uncertainties and develops solutions that are both artistically compelling and supported by the community and compatible with the audience.

The iterative phase model primarily serves as a structural aid for the creativity process and can be used flexibly by experienced users. The test phase is usually followed by an assessment of technical, economic, and cultural feasibility [15].

4 Closing remarks – Design thinking and cultural entrepreneurship

Design thinking has received little attention in the field of cultural entrepreneurship to date. However, it can be considered particularly suitable for combining the desired user orientation with the aesthetic, content-related, or social goals of cultural creators [10]. Design thinking methodically supports key conditions and working methods in the cultural and creative industries. The strong focus on value creation makes it possible to analyze and understand needs, motivations, and contexts of use in depth and to develop innovative, sustainable cultural offerings based on this analysis. This also serves audience development, as the analysis of users can help to diversify the audience. (New) cultural offerings can give more people access to culture and existing audiences can be more closely involved by obtaining feedback [4].

Actors in the cultural and creative industries often work creatively, interdisciplinarily, and experimentally. Creativity is considered a core resource of the industry (ibid.). Design thinking structures this ability to change perspectives and makes it specifically usable for the development of innovative solutions. Creative impulses can thus be transformed into implementable and marketable concepts without limiting creative openness. At the same time, the danger of focusing too strongly on users can restrict artistic autonomy. Offerings can lose their artistic quality through adaptations [11]. The intention of art and cultural offerings to create irritation, novelty, or friction arises over a longer period of time and cannot always be reflected in rapid user feedback.

In addition, the cultural sector operates in fast-paced cycles that are often tied to publications or seasons [7]. Design thinking addresses this by offering iterative, lean development cycles that enable early prototyping, feedback, and rapid adjustments. However, with complex and situational cultural offerings such as exhibitions or performances, it is difficult to test a simple prototype. The audience often reacts differently in the final setting due to the atmosphere or curation, so that early tests may lead to false conclusions.

Overall, cultural entrepreneurs thrive on networks and collaborations [13]. Design thinking benefits

from multidisciplinary collaboration and actively involves different actors in problem analysis and solution finding. Design thinking combines value creation, creative problem solving, iteration, and interdisciplinary collaboration—and thus largely addresses the requirements that are conducive to successful innovation processes in cultural entrepreneurship. In order to exploit the potential of design thinking, it is necessary to balance artistic and economic logic by defining which decisions follow which logic. Prototyping can be enriched by better mapping cultural experiences such as taster formats, public rehearsals, or artifacts, while user research can be deepened with ethnographic methods, narrative interviews, or community support. Overall, it should be emphasized that design thinking must be adapted to the specific characteristics of the arts and culture sector in order to be accepted by cultural practitioners.

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Mittelshmedt Евальд, Вінке Клаудія. Дизайн мислення у сфері культурного підприємництва.

Текст розглядає зростаючу економічну значущість культурних і креативних індустрій та пов'язаний із цим перехід від культурного виробництва, що фінансується державою, до підприємницького, ринково орієнтованого створення цінності. Ця трансформація породжує напруження між іманентною мистецькою логікою культурних професіоналів, які керуються естетичними та соціальними цілями, і підприємницькою логікою, зосередженою на потребах клієнтів та економічній життєздатності. Культурне підприємництво прагне збалансувати ці орієнтації, створюючи пропозиції, що зберігають художню автентичність і водночас залучають аудиторію.

Дизайн-мислення подається як перспективний метод узгодження цих логік. Його сильна орієнтація на користувача забезпечує глибше розуміння потреб аудиторії, сприяє її диверсифікації та структурує притаманні культурній сфері творчі, міждисциплінарні й експериментальні практики. Водночас у тексті визнаються ризики: надмірна увага до зворотного зв'язку від користувачів може загрожувати художній автономії, а швидкі цикли ітерацій не завжди здатні відобразити довгострокові, провокативні наміри мистецтва. Крім того, складні культурні формати важко прототипувати змістовно, оскільки ранні тести можуть не відображати реакції аудиторії у фінальному контексті.

Загалом дизайн-мислення добре узгоджується з колаборативною та мережевою природою культурного підприємництва, однак його ефективне застосування потребує свідомого балансування між художніми та економічними пріоритетами. Текст пропонує адаптувати метод шляхом розширення форматів прототипування та поглиблення якісних досліджень користувачів, щоб точніше відобразити культурний досвід.

Ключові слова: дизайн-мислення, культурне підприємництво, автономія, автентичність, економічна життєздатність.

Mittelstädt Ewald, Wiepcke Claudia. Design Thinking in Cultural Entrepreneurship.

The text examines the increasing economic relevance of the cultural and creative industries and the resulting shift from publicly funded cultural production toward entrepreneurial, market oriented value creation. This transition generates tensions between the art immanent logic of cultural professionals – guided by aesthetic and social aims—and the entrepreneurial logic focused on customer needs and economic viability. Cultural entrepreneurship seeks to balance these competing orientations by developing offerings that maintain artistic authenticity while engaging audiences.

Design thinking is presented as a promising method for reconciling these logics. Its strong user orientation supports deeper insight into audience needs, fosters audience diversification, and structures the inherently creative, interdisciplinary, and experimental practices of cultural work. At the same time, the text acknowledges risks: overemphasis on user feedback may threaten artistic autonomy, and rapid iteration may not capture the long term, friction producing intentions of art. Moreover, complex cultural formats are difficult to prototype meaningfully, as early tests may not reflect final audience responses.

Overall, design thinking aligns with the collaborative and network driven nature of cultural entrepreneurship, but its effective use requires deliberate navigation between artistic and economic priorities. The text suggests adapting the method through richer prototyping formats and deeper qualitative user research to better reflect cultural experiences.

Key words: design thinking, cultural entrepreneurship, autonomy, authenticity, economic viability.

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МІЖДИСЦИПЛІНАРНЕ ПРОЄКТНО-ОРІЄНТОВАНЕ НАВЧАННЯ ТА РОЛЬ СТЕЙКХОЛДЕРІВ (приклад магістерської програми в Австрії)

У сучасному закладі вищої освіти міждисциплінарне навчання стає ключовим трендом, що відповідає на виклики глобалізації, цифрової трансформації, оптимізації та інновації знань, швидких змін на ринку праці. Інтеграція знань з різних дисциплін стимулює розвиток критичного та інноваційного мислення, цілісного знання, комплексність підходів до формування компетентностей, необхідних для сучасного професійного середовища. Впровадження міждисциплінарних проєктів підвищує якість освітніх програм, а також сприяє зростанню довіри до університетських програм. Міждисциплінарне навчання тісно пов'язане з проєктною діяльністю, у тому числі міжнародними проєктами, що дає студентам змогу застосовувати знання з різних дисциплін на практиці, розвивати комплексні компетенції, зокрема навички командної роботи й міжнародної комунікації. Разом із тим, міждисциплінарні навчальні проєкти, як показує досвід, стикаються з низкою структурно-змістовних та комунікативних викликів – обмежені ресурси, оцінювання компетентностей, різниця академічних культур [1; 2].

Останнім часом у дослідженнях було висвітлено так званий концепт «expert-network» у межах підходу Experience and Expertise [3]. У міждисциплінарних проєктах ключову роль відіграють неписані (tacit, тобто «приховані») знання, індивідуальний внесок експертів та спільна інтеграція знань у колективі. Іншими словами, успіх міждисциплінарної роботи забезпечується поєднанням прихованих, інтуїтивних знань фахівців і координацією в мережі експертів. Ця перевага забезпечує ефективність проєктів і сприяє автоматичному зростанню професійних компетентностей здобувачів освіти.

Актуальною є систематизація досвіду реалізації міждисциплінарних проєктів у вищій освіті з метою визначення ефективних підходів до їх інтеграції в освітні програми України та інших країн.

У магістерських програмах Австрії, зокрема в Технічному університеті (Technische Universität - TU/ Wien) у галузі архітектури, активно впроваджуються навчальні проєкти, що інтегрують знання з різних дисциплін для вирішення реальних проблем. Важливу роль у цьому процесі відіграють стейкхолдери – індустріальні партнери, експерти галузі, наукові установи, громадські організації та самі студенти, які залучаються до розробки проєктів, забезпечують практичну значущість завдань і сприяють формуванню компетентностей, необхідних для сучасної професійної діяльності.

Магістерські програми у TU/ Wien підкреслюють міждисциплінарне (interdisciplinary), дослідницьке (research-based) та практично орієнтоване (practice-oriented) навчання, де